

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

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Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETERS
I9205E, 19216E

This certificate provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, unless permission for the publication of an approved extract has been obtained in writing from the Managing Director. It does not of itself impute to the subject of calibration any attributes beyond those shown by the data contained herein.

FOR: Met Office
FAAM
Building 125
Cranfield University
Cranfield
MK43 0AL

For the attention of: Mr A Woolley

DESCRIPTION: Two thermistors

IDENTIFICATION: Type: EI02AL, Serial No. I9205E
Type: EI02BL, Serial No. 19216E
Constructed by FAAM using a Rosemount Engineering housing

PREVIOUS
CERTIFICATE: Not previously calibrated at NPL

DATES OF
CALIBRATION: 15 October to 22 October 2014

Reference: 2014070095

Date of issue: 4 March 2015

Checked by:

Signed:

Name: Dr S A Bell

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

Continuation Sheet

MEASUREMENTS

As requested, each thermistor was measured as follows: the thermistor was connected to a resistor of measured value 100.1 k Ω at 23 °C, and an excitation voltage of nominally 5 V was applied across the two components in series. The resulting signal voltage across the thermistor was measured at a range of temperatures in order to calibrate the sensors. A second value of excitation voltage of nominally $1/\sqrt{2}$ times the first voltage was applied, in order to enable the evaluation of self-heating by the customer. The two thermistors were measured on two parallel channels of an Agilent 34970A data acquisition unit with traceability to National Standards. The measurement duration at each excitation voltage was set to 5 minutes with a data logging interval of 10 seconds. Measurements were carried out at temperatures from -60 °C to +50 °C at intervals of 10 °C. At each temperature, a time of not less than 4 hours was allowed for temperature to equilibrate.

The calibration was carried out in a test chamber, in air, against NPL reference platinum resistance thermometers. Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90).

The results of the calibration are shown in the table below. The values of the applied conditions (temperature and excitation voltage) are shown in the first three columns. The measured signal voltage across the thermistors (I9205E and 19216E) in volts at two different excitation voltages are given in the fourth to the seventh columns. Values in columns identified as “High” relate to the excitation voltage of nominally 5 V, and those identified as “Low” relate to the nominally $1/\sqrt{2}$ excitation voltage. The expanded uncertainties of the temperature measurements are shown in the eighth column. The quoted uncertainties relate to the period of the calibration and are not an indication of the long-term stability of the thermistors.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were 23 °C $\pm$ 3 °C and less than 80 % relative humidity.

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Continuation Sheet

RESULTS

Applied condition			Measurements				Temperature expanded uncertainty / °C
Measured temperature / °C	Excitation voltage / V		Signal voltage / V				
			High		Low		
	High	Low	I9205E	I9216E	I9205E	I9216E	
-59.05	5.000	3.534	4.430	4.433	3.133	3.136	±0.04
-49.36	4.995	3.559	4.038	4.043	2.882	2.887	±0.04
-39.56	4.995	3.534	3.495	3.501	2.481	2.488	±0.04
-29.64	5.008	3.536	2.852	2.858	2.023	2.032	±0.05
-19.60	4.997	3.534	2.177	2.185	1.549	1.559	±0.06
-9.50	4.999	3.532	1.588	1.598	1.128	1.138	±0.05
+0.42	5.000	3.534	1.129	1.139	0.8019	0.8109	±0.04
+10.38	4.998	3.532	0.7887	0.7980	0.5592	0.5668	±0.05
+20.42	4.992	3.536	0.5468	0.5548	0.3883	0.3945	±0.06
+30.41	5.008	3.537	0.3830	0.3894	0.2711	0.2758	±0.05
+40.35	4.997	3.538	0.2697	0.2745	0.1912	0.1947	±0.05
+50.34	4.998	3.534	0.1926	0.1963	0.1363	0.1390	±0.05

UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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